

Antimicrobial Activity, DFT Calculation, ADMET Study and Molecular Docking of Synthetic Chalcone(2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-Bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one

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Abstract

Chalcones, specifically (2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one, were synthesized through the reaction between 4-aminoacetophenone and 3,4,5-trimethoxy benzaldehyde in ethanolic NaOH. Molecular properties such as bond length, bond angle, molecular electrostatic potential surface (MEPs), Mullikan charge, HOMO-LUMO, were investigated using the DFT/B3LYP method with the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set to characterize the electronic states and molecular parameters of the titled molecule. The synthesized compound was evaluated for antimicrobial activities against *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 619), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 96), *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 739), and *Serratia marcescens*. The compound has demonstrated moderate antimicrobial activity against Streptomycin and potential for further drug development. Molecular docking studies were carried out to predict the binding interactions of the compound with the EGFR tyrosine kinase domain (PDB ID: 1M17). Additionally, in silico ADME studies were performed to forecast the pharmacokinetic profile, indicating favorable oral drug-like behavior. The low energy gap between HOMO and LUMO indicates that the molecule is very reactive to chemicals with limited kinetic stability. Molecular docking score is -6.60062kcal/mol and the docking pose have shown hydrophobic interaction with residue LYS721, PHE699. Compound has shown good drug bioavailability because all selected parameters fall within the ADMET range

1.Introduction

Chalcones are abundant in the natural world, ranging from ferns to larger plants. They are unsaturated side chain aromatic compounds that are frequently cytotoxic in vitro [1]. Chalcones have a fully delocalized β -electron system on both benzene rings in addition to conjugated double bonds[2].

Due to their wide range of pharmacological actions, chalcone derivatives, both naturally occurring and synthesized, are currently of interest [3]. Chalcones have a wide range of bioactivities and are easy to synthesize, making them useful structures for drug discovery. An enone bridge connects the two benzene rings (A and B) in their structures [4]. Additionally, by adding substituents to the phenyl ring, one may change the energy of the intense transition in chalcones due to their charge transfer nature in the low-lying π - π^* transition from the phenyl ring to the polyene chain [5]. They are aromatic compounds with an unsaturated side chain and are often cytotoxic in vitro. Chalcones are the initial intermediate used in the biosynthesis of all flavonoids. They are useful for the development of new drugs because they are easily produced using a range of conventional and combinatorial methods with either synthetic or natural materials ([6], [7]). The many pharmacological actions of chalcones, such as their anti-tuberculosis [8], anti-inflammatory [9], anti-diabetic [10], anti-neoplastic [11], anti-fungal [12], anti-cancer [13], antimalarial [14], antioxidant [15], and antibacterial [16] qualities, have been extensively researched.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Material

All the chemicals and solvents used in this work were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

2.2 Synthesis of (2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one

4-aminoacetophenone 1 (1.4797 mmol, 1.0 eq), 3,4,5 tri-methoxy benzaldehyde 2 (1.4797mmol, 1.0 eq), and NaOH (2.95mmol, 2.0 eq) added into 20 mL EtOH at room temperature. as indicated by the chemical pathways in **Scheme 1**. Adding 20 millilitres of water to the reaction mixture after 4 hours produced a yellow solid. After that, filtering used to extract the crude product. Using a combination of ethyl acetate and hexane as the mobile phase, column chromatography used to separate and purify it [17].

Scheme 1. Preparation of (2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one. a) NaOH, ethanol, room temperature, 6hr.

2.3 Computational Detail

The license software programme Gaussian09 was used for all calculations. For the compounds under study, full Optimisations of geometry carried out at the B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) level. using Density FunctionTheory[18]. Graphical representation of MESP, HOMO, and LUMO data in optimized files, were performed using the Gauss view16 visualization program[19].

2.4 Molecular Docking

Docking analysis may be used to study the molecular basis of interactions between target enzymes and synthetic ligands. The title compounds' molecular docking calculations were performed using Discovery Studio 2021, Autodock Vina 4.2, and Schrödinger's Maestro Molecular Modelling platform (version 2022)[20]. The Protein Data Bank website provided the enzyme protein structures (PDB ID: 1M17). All calculations for molecular docking of enzyme-based chalcone were performed within the pH 7.0 ± 2.0 range. This module eliminated every water molecule from the enzyme's crystal structure. Once again, the binding strategies and protein loads inside the enzyme's structure were optimized by the use of this module. Proteins' active sites have been identified. During the interaction, mobility was granted to the proteins in the active area. Molecular docking calculations were performed using the LigPrep module ([21],[22])after the drawing of the molecules. This module yielded the molecular geometries of the title compound, their 3D structures, and their proper protonation state at physiological pH. Following the preparation of the title compound, molecular docking simulations of enzymes with the investigated title compound were performed using the Glide docking module. The pharmacological characteristics of chalcone will be investigated subsequent to the computation of the molecules' biological activity against enzymes[23].

2.5 ADMET Study

Additionally, we have carried out the ADMET (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity) Te Pfizer study. The Rule of Five is a general guideline used to assess whether an inhibitor with certain physiological and pharmacological characteristics will function as an oral active medication in humans ([24],[25]). Preclinical safety and pharmacokinetics studies are necessary to guarantee the safety profile of candidate compounds in medication development. Experimental assessments are subject to time and budget constraints, even with the widespread use of in vivo and in vitro studies. Over the last several decades, in silico estimates have been

produced for each of these preclinical objectives. Still, very few web-based tools have brought together many models into an easy-to-use, one-step platform to help researchers properly assess potential drug candidates[26].

2.6 Antibacterial Study

The antimicrobial efficacy of the target molecule was evaluated against both Gram-positive bacteria, including *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 619) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 96), as well as Gram-negative strains such as *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 739) and *Serratia marcescens*. To assess its effectiveness, the title compound underwent testing using the agar well diffusion method. This involved inoculating N-agar plates with active cultures of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Sterile blank disks (6 mm diameter) were then impregnated with a solution containing synthesized compounds at a concentration of 2 µg/mL, dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). These disks were subsequently incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Following the incubation period, the diameter of the inhibition zones surrounding each well containing the compound was measured and compared with control groups. Streptomycin was employed as the standard reference drug for comparison of antibacterial activity. The size of the inhibition zones around the wells containing the target compound was juxtaposed with those around the wells containing streptomycin, enabling the assessment of the compound's antibacterial effectiveness against the selected bacterial strains.

3 Result and Discussion

3.1(2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-Bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one:

It preferable to use elemental analysis data and spectroscopic techniques such as IR, ¹H-NMR, and ¹³C-NMR to confirm the structure of the title compounds in the previous article [27].

3.2 Computational Study

Fig. 1 displays the optimized geometric structure of the chemical mentioned above. The title compound's molecular structure is a member of the C₁ symmetry point group. This compound's optimized structural characteristics were determined using B3LYP and 6-31G+(d,p) basis sets. Gaussian09 software was used to calculate the molecular orbital energies of the chemical in question. The resulting energy values are shown in **Fig. 2**. The three-dimensional HOMO-LUMO energy values that were determined were $E_{\text{HOMO}} = -0.22432$ eV, $E_{\text{LUMO}} = -0.08329$ eV, and the gap between them was $\Delta E_{\text{gap}} = 0.14103$ eV. This low gap indicates that the molecule is very reactive to chemicals and has limited kinetic stability. Using DFT/B3LYP level with 6-311+G(d, p) basis set, the molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) surface projected over the optimized electronic structure of title compound to predict the reactive sites of electrophilic and nucleophilic assault on the examined molecule. **Fig. 3** displays the three-dimensional MEP map of the title compound, which includes colour codes ranging from $-5.877e-2$ to $5.877e-2$ eV, the darkest red and blue. The carbonyl oxygen (O₃₀) was the primary location of the most negative electrostatic potential area, suggesting potential sites for electrophilic assault. Conversely, the hydrogen was the primary location of the most positive region, suggesting potential sites for nucleophilic attack.

Fig. 1. Optimized Structure using B3LYP with 6-31G+(d,p) basis sets

Fig 2.(a) HOMO and (b) LUMO of optimized structure using B3LYP with 6-31G+(d,p)

Fig. 3. (a) a (a) ESP of Optimized Structure using B3LYP with 6-31G+(d,p) basis sets (b)

3.3 Molecular Docking

In the current work, present compound is subjected to molecular docking against the X-Ray Crystal structure of the EGF Receptor kinase domain (PDB ID: 1M17) as a receptor for a molecular docking. Just before the docking calculations, the active residues in the receptors were detected as follows: LEU694, ASP831, THR830, VAL702, THR766, LEU764, MET769, PRO770, LEU768, GLY772, GLU738, MET742, ALA719, LYS721. In this study, the title compound has good docking score -6.60062. Moreover, the docking pose showed hydrophobic interaction with residue LYS721, PHE699 [Fig.4(c)]. With further research, this finding may be used to produce a number of useful medicinal molecules.

Fig.4 Schrodinger: (a) 3-D interaction (b) 2-D interaction

Discovery Studio: (c) Hydrophobic interaction, (d) H-Bond interaction and (e) Ionizability (f) 3-D interactions

Table 1. Docking study of title compound with EGF receptor kinase domain (1M17)

Ligand	Glide Score	Amino acid interaction	hydrophobicity	Bond length
	-6.60062	PHE699	2.8	1.46037
		VAL702	4.2	1.45403
		LYS721	-3.9	1.464
		MET742	1.9	1.46208
		ASP831	-3.5	1.46422

3.4 Drug-likeness Prediction

The Lipinski rule (RO5 rule), which is based on several parameters like MW (molecular weight), TPSA (topological surface area), HBA (hydrogen bonding acceptors), HBD (hydrogen bonding donors), lipophilicity, logP, nRot (number of rotational bonds), Violations, etc., is used to analyze physicochemical properties. For a medicine to have adequate bioavailability, it must meet the following criteria: MW < 500 Dalton, TPSA (TPSA) ≤ 140 Å², HBD < 5, HBA < 10, and Violations < 4. The primary physicochemical properties of intestinal absorption and brain penetration influence have been investigated using the "BOILED-EGG method" (Fig. 5). There was no evidence of skin sensitization, AMES, or renal toxicity in any of the tested derivatives. The molecule with the title showed good drug bioavailability, since they fall within the ADMET range (Tables 2).

Table 2. physicochemical properties calculated by ADMET

(a)

compound	MW	nRot	HBA	HBD	TPSA	MLogP	Lipinski rule violation
	301.01	3	1	1	43.09	3.42	0

Fig.5. (a) the boiled egg plot (b) The bioavailability radar

2.3 Antimicrobial Activity

The significant inhibitory activity of previously synthesized compound [27] against *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 619) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 96), and *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 739) and *Serratia marcescens* is seen. It was observed that the antibacterial activity of against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria was indistinguishable. The title molecule had inhibition zones of the range 18-32mm which is shown in table 3.

Table 3 In vitro antimicrobial screening of (2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-Bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one

Compound ^b	Microorganism ^a			
	Gram positive		Gram negative	
3	B.Subtilis	S. Aureus	E.Coli	S.Marcscens
	Streptomycin	18	22	29
	19	21	30	34

^a = % growth inhibition

^b = concentration 1.2 mg per disk

4. Conclusion

This research study encompasses the synthesis, characterization, and evaluation of the anti-bacterial activity of (2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-Bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one against both Gram-positive bacteria, including *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 619) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 96), as well as Gram-negative strains such as *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 739) and *Serratia marcescens*. Additionally, molecular docking studies of the target compound revealed its optimal binding interaction with amino acid residues LEU694, ASP831, THR830, VAL702, THR766, LEU764, MET769, PRO770, LEU768, GLY772, GLU738, MET742, ALA719, and LYS721 of the EGF Receptor kinase domain (PDB ID: 1M17), exhibiting a very favorable glide score of -6.60062 kcal/mol. Computational theoretical calculations were conducted using DFT/B3LYP with 6-31G+(d,p) basis sets, revealing a HOMO-LUMO energy gap ($\Delta E_{\text{gap}} = 0.14103$ eV) that reflects the chemical activity of the molecule. Furthermore, ADMET research suggests that (2E)-1-(4-Aminophenyl)-3-(4-Bromo phenyl)-2-propen-1-one are a pharmacologically active group of compounds when administered orally, with minimal risk of toxicity such as genetic

mutation or cardiotoxicity. Results indicate that the title compound exhibits low ability to penetrate the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and is a promising candidate due to its compliance with the Lipinski Rule.

List Of Abbreviations

DFT	=	Density Functional Theory
HOMO	=	Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital
LUMO	=	Lowest Occupied Molecular Orbital
MESP	=	Molecular Electrostatic Potential
BBB	=	Blood-Brain Barrier
HIA	=	Human Intestinal Absorption
ADMET	=	Absorption Distribution Metabolism Excretion Toxicity
PDB	=	Protein Data Bank

Conflict Of Interest

The authors affirm that none of the research findings disclosed in this study have been subject to influence from any identifiable conflicting financial interests or personal affiliations.

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